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ORGANIZATION OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF CADETS

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes using traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching cadets at the military establishments. This article uses modern methods of teaching and training military personnel.

Keywords: *pedagogical technology, educational process, cadet, manage the lesson.*

The relevance of the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the organization of the educational process in the military education system comes from the following necessity:

- training of military specialist personnel at the level of world requirements;
- adaptation to the requirements of modern military action;
- selection, development of approaches to the educational system and methods of conducting lessons;
- the role of the teacher in the educational process, the demand for the educational process, the achieved result and others.

The lesson is the main organizational form of giving knowledge to cadets. What should be presented at the lessons? What results should today's teacher achieve in the lesson? What knowledge should the cadet take away from the lesson? Today's lesson should teach a cadet to cultivate and creative abilities, expand mental potential, make up a scientific worldview and be able to correctly perceive every innovation. Therefore, it is of paramount importance how the teacher-cadet relationship is organized at the lesson, the teacher is able to correctly choose methods and tools for the implementation of educational goals in the lesson. Today at the lesson, the main task of the teacher is to manage the lesson. In order to manage the lesson, the training and methodological support in the lesson must be complete. The teacher must correctly set the goals of the lesson. It is important that educational tasks are interrelated with teaching tasks at the lesson and form scientific worldviews and beliefs as a result of the content of certain concepts, ideas. At the lesson, it is necessary to create conditions for the free, creative work of cadets. To do this, it is necessary to correctly and accurately select the educational material for each part of the lessons.

The use of non – traditional educational methods-interactive methods, along with traditional educational methods, is one of the important conditions for improving the effectiveness of the lesson. It is extremely important that cadets are allowed to work creatively when using interactive techniques. Interactive methods serve to form free thinking, creative abilities of the cadet. Cadets quickly and independently master new knowledge and concepts when using these techniques. They can prove that their thoughts are true or wrong. When using interactive methods, the following requirements should be observed:

- the lesson should be aimed at solving educational and developmental goals and tasks based on the curriculum;
- it is important that the lesson goals are fully solved based on experience in practice, when the methods are used;
- it is necessary that the method complies with the standards of morality based on the criteria for;
- when using interactive techniques, it is necessary to achieve the minimum amount of time spent, guided by didactic principles.

The most basic basis of modern pedagogical technologies depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the cadet so that they can achieve a guaranteed result from the established goal in cooperation, that is, in the process of teaching, each educational technology used to achieve a guaranteed result by the goal can organize cooperative activities between the teacher and the cadet, if they can work creatively, research, analyze, evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for their activities of this kind, then this teaching is the basis of the process.

It is up to them that the teacher and the cadet choose what technology they have in achieving the result from the goal, since the main goal of both parties is clear: the level of knowledge of the cadets, the character of the group, the technology used depending on the circumstances is selected, for example, to achieve the result.

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